

Social Network Analysis

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Introduction

Social Network analysis is an investigation made on social structures through the use of networks. The field of social network analysis is the dynamic and highly adaptable combination of techniques that let us quantify and recognize the complex structures and flows of relationships, thoughts, and things between people around the world.

Social network analysis has emerged as a critical technique in modern sociology. It has also gained an important following in economics, geography, history, information science, organizational studies, anthropology, biology, demography, communication studies, sociolinguistics, political science, social psychology, development studies, and computer science and is now usually available as a consumer tool.

History

Social network analysis has its theoretical roots in the work of early sociologists such as George Simmel, who wrote about the importance of studying patterns of relationships that connect social actors. Social scientists have used the concept of "social networks" since early in the 20th century to connote complex sets of relationships between members of social systems at all scales, from interpersonal to international.

In the 1930s Jacob Morano and Helen Jennings organized basic analytical methods. In 1954, John Arundel Barnes caused using the term systematically to denote patterns of ties, encompassing thoughts traditionally used by the public and those used by social scientists: bounded groups (e.g., tribes, families) and social categories (e.g., gender, ethnicity). Scholars such as Ronald Burt, Kathleen Carley,

Douglas R. White, Rapoport, Barry Wellman Harrison White, Mark Granovetter, David Krackhardt, Edward Laumann, and Anatol expanded the use of systematic social network analysis.

Network Analysis in the use of Various Application

Social Network Analysis is used in many forms of applications. As the network is a great useful source, many application runs through networks. In the private sector, business uses social network

analysis to support activities such as “Information system,” “Business Process,” and “Information Systems.”

Public sectors use network analysis in the development of leader engagement strategies, analysis of individual and group engagement, and community-solving problems.

Security Application

Social Network Analysis is also used mainly in security forces. It is used to analyze the terrorist gangs and networks all over the world to every security agencies hanging on the present. After the initial mapping, os social network analyze is done to track the unrecognized forces.

E.g., The National Security Agency and FBI agents of USA tracked call detail records of terrorists to catch them, and they finished it in 2011.

Internet Applications

Social Network Analysis has also been implemented in understanding online behavior by individuals. As in the commerce lines, this collected information is sent to the respective corporate. with those information they select their customers.

Hyperlinks can be used to analyze the connections between websites or web pages to examine how information flows as individuals negative web. The connective has been analyzed through hyperlinks.

Flowcharts on Network Analysis

As like the above image, the network connects the group of systems, users information, ideas, etc...

Conclusion

As a Business Entrepreneur, it’s the right time to involve yourselves into Business network and analysis and attain the respective knowledge or customer for your outsource. Start a website. Post your outsource. Search for your valuable customer through the network

“Networking is more about farming than it is about hunting.”

-Dr. Ivan Minser, BNI